

FUNCTION AND ROLE OF BUILDING LINES (RED LINES) AND BUILDING REGULATION LINES IN URBAN PLANNING

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Abstract. This article considers the problem of observing the boundaries of a land plot and private housing construction during its construction. In particular, compliance with red lines and other lines of urban planning regulation when placing residential and other buildings on the site. The article discusses the composition of the documents of the project of detailed planning of the city, compiled by the scale: 1:2000 project of red lines defining the boundaries between built-up neighborhoods and driveways with sidewalks and lawns. As a result of comparing the coordinates, design and executive, a conclusion is made about the accuracy of the transfer.

Keywords: red lines, control line, vertical layout.

ФУНКЦИЯ И РОЛЬ ЛИНИЙ ЗАСТРОЙКИ (КРАСНЫХ ЛИНИЙ) И ЛИНИЙ РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ ЗАСТРОЙКИ В ГОРОДСКОМ ПЛАНИРОВАНИИ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается проблема соблюдения границ земельного участка и частного жилищного строительства при его возведении. В частности, соблюдение красных линий и других линий градостроительного регламента при размещении жилых и иных зданий на участке. В статье рассматривается состав документов проекта детальной планировки города, составленного по проекту красных линий масштаба 1:2000, определяющих границы между застроенными микрорайонами и проездами с тротуарами и газонами. В результате сравнения координат, проектных и исполнительных, делается вывод о точности переноса.

Ключевые слова: красные линии, контрольная линия, вертикальная компоновка.

Building lines (red lines) mark the boundaries of communal areas; they are subject to the stating, change, or cancellation in the documentation on territory planning [2].

The boundary between the street and the block is called the building (red) line. This concept is of great importance from the point of view of geodetic services since in the process of realizing a planning project (of streets, squares, blocks, etc.), it is precisely these boundaries that are stacked out on the locality.

The building regulation line is located parallel to the red line at a distance from the latter of at least 6 m for main streets and 3 m for residential streets. Protrusions of structures beyond the building regulation lines are not allowed.

Thus, spaces from the red line to the control line are set, which are then planted with trees. They are arranged for hygienic purposes and for the placement of underground engineering networks (water supply, heat and gas supply networks, cables, etc.).

In cramped conditions, red lines and regulation lines can be combined.

The documents of the project of a detailed plan of the city, drawn up on a scale of 1: 2000, shows a project of red lines that define the boundaries between built-up blocks and driveways with sidewalks and lawns.

When drawing red lines on a topographic plan, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the facades or other structural elements located on a particular site do not go beyond the line toward the street. Plans to be applied can be scaled from 1:500 to 1:2000. It is necessary to clearly check the placement of lines in order to avoid controversial, problematic situations when there is a discrepancy between new marks and the ones that have already been put into land management documents. The referencing of the red lines project to the terrain is designed using buildings and structures existing in situ and on the plan. Such buildings are called "basic". Figure 1 shows a fragment of the project of red lines and basic buildings A, B, and C. In the absence of basic buildings, the project of red lines is related to the situation or relief.

Fig 1. The draft of the master plan considering the prospective development of the inhabited locality for 25-30 years

In parallel with the approval of the master plan, a draft of priority stages and a detailed planning project are developed, with an account for the development of the territory for a 5-year perspective. At the same time, working drawings of the development are plotted, taking into account the prospects for 1-2 years.

Thus, the development of the territory allotted for an inhabited locality is conducted gradually in separate isolated areas, often at considerable distances from each other.

In order not to disturb the overall design and architectural composition while building up the territory in parts, analytical preparations are made for the transfer of the red lines project into the site throughout the whole territory. Analytical preparation consists in calculating the coordinates of all the corners of blocks along the red lines or the points of intersection of the axes of drives in a single city system.

The starting points for analytical preparation are the coordinates of the corners of the basic buildings, determined at the site from field traverse points.

To obtain the coordinates of the corners of the blocks along the red lines between the corners of the basic buildings, theodolite-type passages or passage systems are outlined. The lengths of the lines and the angles of rotation in such passages are chosen according to the dimensions of the blocks, the width of the passages and the values between the axes of passages indicated on the red lines project.

On the site of future construction works, the corners of the blocks of red lines or the points of intersection of the axes of passages along the calculated coordinates are transferred to the site from the signs of field traverse. In those places where it is impossible or difficult to transfer the signs to the site of the red lines project directly from field traverse points, special theodolite passages are laid, from which the points of the red lines project are transferred to the site [3].

After the completion of the geodetic survey and transferring the project to the site, control theodolite passages or systems of passages forming the nodal points are laid on all design points of the locality. The discrepancy between the actual coordinates of the points obtained after adjusting the theodolite traverses for a built-up area should not exceed 20 cm and for an undeveloped area - 30 cm. If the design point is put and controlled from the same line of geodetic control, then the deviation of the coordinates of the control passage from the design ones should not exceed 5 cm in a high-rise building zone, 8 cm in a low-rise building zone, and 10 cm in a village building zone.

The corners of the red lines in the site are fixed in the same way as the points of surveying theodolite traverses. In large cities, work on transferring red lines into the site is conducted by the geodetic services of the city. Set points located on the site are transferred to construction organizations according to the act.

In large cities, with a large scale of construction, the surveying of the main axes of buildings and structures is also performed by the city's geodetic services.

In large cities, under construction management, special geodetic services are organized, which draw up projects for the production of geodetic works both at the construction site and during the construction of the building. This project provides for the places and methods for fixing the main and auxiliary axes of buildings, and the placement of the elevated datum points on the construction site, and methods for determining their marks. Methods are also provided for transferring the geodetic base to the tiers of construction works and openings in the floors, which must be made for geodetic stakeouts.

Vertical planning, that is, the arrangement and change in the relief of the territory being developed, is a section of each stage of the design of populated areas, their individual parts, sections, and the street road network. The defining document of the city vertical planning project is the vertical planning scheme, which provides for design solutions along the axes of the designed passages in the form of design marks of the intersection points of the axes and bends of the longitudinal profile. The scheme shows the distances between the points of the profile bend and between the points of intersection of the axes, indicating the slopes in thousandths and the direction of water run-off. Projects of transverse profiles of streets are attached to the scheme.

The working draft of the vertical layout is based on the vertical layout scheme. It includes longitudinal profiles along the axes of streets and chutes, transverse profiles at pickets and in

characteristic places, as well as a cartogram of earthworks and a ground motion scheme. On the vertical planning project, the marks of the finished floor elevation of the first floor, the design, and the existing marks of the corners of buildings and structures are indicated.

Stakeout for vertical planning is carried out from the red lines. Red lines define the boundaries between micro-districts, blocks, industrial zone, technical zone and water basin zone; they define the directions of streets and driveways and, in turn, depend on their direction.

The red lines project is drawn up on a topographic plan on a scale of 1: 2000 - 1: 500. The defining elements of the project are the length of the red lines between the corners of blocks or the boundaries of micro-districts, the width of streets and driveways, the values of the angles between the red lines, the radii and elements of the curves along the red lines, dimensions that define the shape of squares and parks. In the course of preparing the project for transfer to the site, the coordinates of the corners of blocks and the boundaries of micro-districts are calculated along red lines, break points of red lines and alignment points on long straight lines, points of intersection of the axes of streets and driveways, directional angles of straight lines, as well as the coordinates of the main points of circular curves along red lines in a single urban coordinate system.

Coordinates are calculated from the points of previously approved or existing red lines and from the corners of basic buildings and structures. The coordinates of the corners of the basic buildings and structures are calculated after field measurements from the points of the urban geodetic control. The numbers of the turning and alignment points of the red lines, the values of their coordinates, directional angles and lengths of the straight lines, curve elements, the width and numbers of the projected passages, the names of the projected zones and other building elements are indicated on the plan of the red lines.

The red lines and axes of streets and driveways are transferred to the site from the points of an existing or specially created geodetic control point. Immediately prior to the placement in the site, the position of the red lines is checked and clarified in accordance with the approved planning project. The presence and condition of geodetic control points are checked on the locality. If there are no geodetic control points in the area of the forthcoming work or there are not enough of them, traverse or theodolite passages are laid, which are necessary for staking out.

The errors in placing the red lines points and the axes of the passages in relation to the points of geodetic control should not be more than [25]: 5 cm - in areas of high-rise buildings; 8 cm - in areas of low-rise buildings; 10 cm - in an undeveloped area.

In accordance with the specific conditions, a geodetic project is drawn up for a detailed stacking of the red lines and axes of passages. The main staking method is the polar coordinate method, although the cross bearing (intersection) and perpendicular methods are sometimes used.

From the solution of the inverse geodesic problem, using the coordinates of the geodetic control point and the coordinates of the axis point of the red line x_2, y_2 the directional angle α_{1-2} and the length of the line d_{1-2} are determined:

$$\operatorname{tg}\alpha_{1-2} = \frac{y_2 - y_1}{x_2 - x_1} \quad \text{and} \quad d_{1-2} = \frac{y_2 - y_1}{\sin \alpha_{1-2}} = \frac{x_2 - x_1}{\cos \alpha_{1-2}}.$$

This data is used to find stacking elements and draw up a stacking draft. Tracing on the site is performed using a theodolite and a steel tape measure. Angles are built in one step with an angle

to the right and an angle to the left. When plotting design distances on the site, corrections for calibration, temperature, and slope of the terrain are taken into account.

In some cases, it is convenient to first stack the axes of the streets on the terrain, and then, from them mark the red lines. If ground or underground structures (tramlines, sewerage, etc.) are located along the axis of the street, then for the convenience, an offset axis is indicated instead of the true axis. The offset axis is built parallel to the true axis in a place convenient to use and fix.

The points of the red line and the axis of the passage are fixed in the site with temporary signs (tubes, pins, crutches, stakes). In the built-up area, the axis of the passage and the red lines are painted on the walls of buildings and other structures with which the lines intersect. Linear measurements tie signs of fastening to local objects. An outline is drawn up with the results of stacking; in an undeveloped area, fixing signs are dug around. The control of the breakdown of red lines and axes of streets is realized according to the results of the executive passage, laid according to the signs of fixing. As a result of comparing design and executive coordinates, a conclusion is drawn about the accuracy of the transfer. After laying the executive passage, an executive drawing is plotted for transferring the axes of passages and red lines to the site. The drawing indicates the points of geodetic control, the position of the points of the axes and red lines, the distances between them, and the data of fixing to local objects.

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